

Rotatory Power of Brucine Derivatives of Some Isonitroso Ketones. Part III. Brucine Derivatives of α -Chloro- and α -Bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenones

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Brucine derivatives of α -chloro- and α -bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenones have been prepared, characterised, and their rotatory powers determined in chloroform and pyridine. The effect of different substituents on the optical rotatory power in these compounds has been discussed.

In previous communications^{1,2} the rotatory powers of brucine derivatives of isonitrosoacetophenone and α -chloro- and α -bromo- α -isonitrosoacetophenones were described and the effect of some groups on the magnitude of rotatory power² in the case of brucine derivatives of α -chloro- and α -bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methylacetophenones was discussed. In the present communication this work has been extended to the study of rotatory powers of brucine derivatives of α -chloro- and α -bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenones.

EXPERIMENTAL

The isonitroso ketones, prepared by the method described earlier³, were mixed with brucine in equimolecular proportions in ethanol-chloroform mixture when salt-like compounds crystallised. The characteristics of pure brucine derivatives of α -chloro- (A) and α -bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenone (B) obtained are described below.

*Brucine Derivatives of α -Chloro- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenone (A).*—It is light brown in colour, m.p. 265° (decomp.). (Found: C, 56.46; H, 5.74; N, 6.38. $C_{32}H_{34}O_7N_3Cl \cdot 4H_2O$ requires C, 56.51; H, 5.58; N, 6.18%).

(B).—It is light brown in colour, m.p. 237° (decomp.). (Found: C, 55.62; H, 5.95; N, 5.80. $C_{32}H_{34}O_7N_3Br \cdot 2H_2O$ requires C, 55.81; H, 5.52; N 6.10%).

Both these compounds are fairly soluble in chloroform and pyridine, sparingly soluble in ethanol, and practically insoluble in water, ethyl acetate, benzene, acetone, carbon tetrachloride, dekalin, dioxane, and ether.

Measurements of the rotatory power were carried out in a 2-dm tube in chloroform and in pyridine. For the sake of comparison, approximately similar concentrations and temperatures were used. The results are recorded in Table I.

1. Perti *et al.*, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci.*, under publication.
2. *Ibid.*, under publication.
3. Singh *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1931, **8**, 345.

The rotatory power data on analysis by usual methods show that the dispersion is simple and can be expressed by one-term Drude's equation of the type:

$$[\alpha] = \frac{k}{\lambda^2 - \lambda_0^2}$$

where k is rotation constant and λ_0 dispersion constant. The calculated equations in each case are shown in Table I. There is good agreement between the proposed equations and the observed rotatory power for different wave lengths employed in measurements.

TABLE I
Rotatory powers of brucine derivatives.

Solvent:	α -Chloro- α -isonitroso- <i>p</i> -methoxy-acetophenone.		α -Bromo- α -isonitroso- <i>p</i> -methoxy-acetophenone.	
	Chloroform	Pyridine	Chloroform	Pyridine
Conc. (g./100 ml):	1.0944	1.1040	1.0600	1.0620
Temp.:	19.5°	19.5°	20.5°	20.5°
Calc. dispersion eq. $[\alpha]_{\lambda}$:	2.221	5.405	2.234	3.888
	$\lambda^2 - 0.1666$	$\lambda^2 - 0.1085$	$\lambda^2 - 0.1578$	$\lambda^2 - 0.1060$
Wave length (λ).	Obs. $[\alpha]_{\lambda}$.	Obs. $[\alpha]_{\lambda}$.	Obs. $[\alpha]_{\lambda}$.	Obs. $[\alpha]_{\lambda}$.
Cd ₄₈₀₀	..	44.38°	..	..
Cd ₅₀₈₆	-24.21°	-36.23°	-22.16°	-25.42°
Hg ₅₄₆₁	-16.90°	-28.53°	-16.02°	-20.24°
Hg ₅₇₈₀	-13.24°	-24.00°	-12.73°	-16.94°
Na ₅₈₉₃	-12.33°	-22.64°	-11.79°	-16.00°
Li ₆₁₀₄	-10.96°	-20.38°	-10.37°	-14.59°
Na ₆₄₀₂	- 9.13°	-18.11°	- 8.96°	-12.71°
Cd ₆₄₃₈	- 8.68°	-17.66°	- 8.49°	-12.24°
Li ₆₇₀₈	- 7.76°	-15.85°	- 7.54°	-11.29°

DISCUSSION

The rotatory powers of brucine derivatives of isonitroso ketones have been compared in Table II

TABLE II
Comparison of rotatory powers.

Brucine derivatives.	Sp. rotation for Hg ₅₄₆₁ .		*Mol. rotation for Hg ₅₄₆₁ .	
	Chloroform.	Pyridine.	Chloroform.	Pyridine.
1 B- α -chloro- α -isonitroso-A	11.63°	28.94°	79.84°	198.6°
2 B- α -chloro- α -isonitroso- <i>p</i> -methyl-A	16.66°	25.37°	110.5°	168.3°
3 B- α -chloro- α -isonitroso- <i>p</i> -methoxy-A	16.90°	28.53°	114.6°	193.6°
4 B- α -bromo- α -isonitroso-A	18.59°	20.12°	122.3°	191.6°
5 B- α -bromo- α -isonitroso- <i>p</i> -methyl-A	13.40°	28.64°	87.62°	187.3°
6 B- α -bromo- α -isonitroso- <i>p</i> -methoxy-A	16.02°	20.24°	110.3°	139.3°

*1/100 (M.W. $\times$ sp. rotation).

N. B. Compounds No. (1) and (4) described in Part I¹; compounds No. (2) and (5) described in Part II².

B denotes brucine and A, acetophenone.

ROTATORY POWER OF BRUCINE DERIVATIVES OF SOME ISONITROSO KETONES

Brucine derivative of α -chloro- α -isonitroso-*p*-methylacetophenone differs from that of α -chloro- α -isonitrosoacetophenone in having Me in place of H in the *para* position of the benzene part of the molecule. If in place of Me we have OMe we obtain brucine derivative of α -chloro- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenone. A similar structural relationship exists among brucine derivatives of α -bromo- α -isonitrosoacetophenone, α -bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methylacetophenone, and α -bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenone.

In the case of brucine derivatives of α -chloro- α -isonitrosoacetophenone and α -chloro- α -isonitroso-*p*-methylacetophenone, we find that replacement of H by Me in *para* position of the benzene part of the molecule causes an enhancement in the magnitude of rotation in chloroform and a decrease in pyridine. Similar results are obtained if we consider the replacement of H by OMe. Quantitatively, however, the differences are smaller when H is replaced by OMe than by Me. In the case of the corresponding bromo compounds, namely, brucine derivatives of α -bromo- α -isonitrosoacetophenone, α -bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methylacetophenone, and α -bromo- α -isonitroso-*p*-methoxyacetophenone, we find that replacement of H by either Me or OMe causes a decrease in the magnitude of rotatory power when the solvent is either chloroform or pyridine. Thus the order of the rotatory power of the substituent groups in the *para* position of the benzene part of the molecule is as shown in Table III.

TABLE III

Isonitrosoacetophenones.	Chloroform.	Pyridine.
Chloro-	OMe > Me > H	H > OMe > Me
Bromo-	H > OMe > Me	H > OMe > Me

In an earlier study in the case of amino derivatives of oxymethylenecamphor, Singh *et al.*³ found that the replacement of H by Me caused a decrease in the magnitude of rotatory power. Singh *et al.*⁴ studied the amino derivatives of Reychler's acid and observed that replacement of H by Me in the *para* position of the benzene part of the molecule resulted in a slight decrease in the magnitude of rotatory power when measurements were made in water, methanol, ethanol, pyridine, or chloroform as solvents. The differences, however, were quantitatively small. Perti and Agnihotri⁵ found that replacement of H by OMe in the *para* position of the benzene part of anilino-(+)-camphor β sulphonate caused a decrease in the magnitude of rotatory power in water or chloroform, but a slight increase was noticed in ethanol. When quantitative comparisons are made in the case of anilino and substituted anilino derivatives of Reychler's acid, we find that the order of the rotatory power in water, ethanol, or chloroform, for which the data are available, is H > Me > OMe.

From the above discussion it is evident that the replacement of H by Me or OMe in a part of the molecule, away from the asymmetric centre, has a tendency to cause a lowering in the magnitude of rotatory power. Quantitatively speaking, the differences tend to be smaller, the greater the distance of these substituents from the asymmetric centre. Consequently, these small differences may not be very well marked in all solvents. The magni-

4. *Lahore Phil. Soc.*, 1964, 6, 15.

5. *Vijnan Parishad Anusandhan Patrika*, 1958, 1, 199.

tude of rotatory power is known to be influenced very much by polar solvents⁶ and it is to this effect that one must attribute the discrepancy observed in the case of chloro-isonitrosoacetophenones in chloroform

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